

Africa and Asia Programmes – National COVID testing: Kenya

This map illustrates the key stakeholders, relationships and information flows that were captured as part of consultations with Wellcome-funded researchers. This map is illustrative only and based on the understanding and perspectives of consulted Wellcome-funded researchers at the time of engagement. It may not comprehensively represent all stakeholders or relationships in the ecosystem, and actual information flows may vary across different contexts, institutions, or research programmes.

Legend

- Research funders
- Research performing organisations

- Universities
- Government
- Intergovernmental organisations

- Public health bodies
- Public engagement
- Denotes groups of organisations

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Africa and Asia Programmes – National COVID testing: Thailand

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Africa and Asia Programmes – National COVID testing: Vietnam

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COVID-19 surveillance in West and Central Africa: Ghana

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Funding and coordination

Sample collection

Genomic sequencing

Data analysis

Data sharing

Research uptake

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COVID-19 Genomics – MENA: Saudi Arabia

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Epidemic Intelligence in South Asia: Nepal

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Establishing genomic epidemiology hubs across Latin America: Brazil

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Establishing genomic epidemiology hubs across Latin America: Costa Rica

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Genomic Surveillance program for SARS-CoV-2: Consortium of India and Sri Lanka: India

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Genomic Surveillance program for SARS-CoV-2: Consortium of India and Sri Lanka: Sri Lanka

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